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- Poetry
- Short Stories
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“SPIRITUALITY IN IMPROVING YOUNG ADULTS’ MENTAL HEALTH”

Numerous studies say that spirituality is a protective factor that improves and strengthens mental health (Aggarwal, Morgan, Patton & Reavley, 2023). Our connectedness to God and our religious practices help improve our mental health. Spirituality helps us realize that we are not alone in facing the challenges presented to us. The idea that a higher power guides us in difficult times brings hope and inner peace. Furthermore, faith communities serve as our support group. Our church has been proven to be a place where we go for counseling and meditation. It is an organization that implements programs that strengthen our community. On the other hand, understanding and practicing religious teachings shape our view of the world positively, strengthening our mental health. Overall, spirituality fosters connection, meaning, and purpose for everyone.

In the discussion of mental health, we can't avoid talking about self-harm and suicide, especially among adolescents and young adults. According to the University of the Philippines Population Institute (2022), the Filipino youth have worse levels of mental health today nationwide, in which close to one in five Filipino youth aged 15-24 have suicidal ideation or have thought of ending their life. With this problem, spirituality can play an important role as a protective factor in preventing suicide through reflections on hope and purpose in life.

As an educator assigned to the guidance office in a State University in the province of Negros Oriental, I have seen the positive effects of spirituality in improving the mental health of my students. Many have come to counseling feeling hopeless, unable to see a path in their problems. By helping them see things from a lens of optimism grounded by spirituality, it has combat feelings of isolation, alienation, and suicidal ideation.

In the end, spirituality can play an important role in the lives of many Filipinos, especially in their mental health, when integrated with other stress management strategies. It negates the effects of stress and self-harm.

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